

Table 3: Summary of characteristics of studies included in the review

Authors and Year	Study Setting/ Country	Study Aim	Study design	Data Collection Methods	Participants and Description	Sample Size	Key Findings (as they relate to research question)
Ober et al. 2025[23]	South Africa	To identify positive deviant characteristics in public PHC facilities with high ART retention and use these insights to design a compassion-focused intervention to improve staff and patient experience and retention	Qualitative	In-depth interviews, Focus Group Discussions, Patient shadowing visits, and Facility observations	Facility leaders, healthcare providers, patient with HIV (PWH), and Public primary care facilities	11 facility leaders, 29 healthcare providers, 45 patient participants, 23 patient shadowing visits, and 6 public primary care facilities (3 high- and 3 low-retention)	<p>Positive patient-provider relationships and supportive facility environments contributed to higher 12-month ART retention and greater patient willingness to return to facilities.</p> <p>High-retention facilities were characterized by compassionate, respectful, team-oriented staff and collaborative relationships with management. Staff felt supported and connected, contributing to positive patient-provider interactions and greater willingness of patients to return to facilities.</p> <p>Low-retention facilities reported scolding, disrespect, burnout, stress, and poor teamwork. Staff felt isolated and needed more managerial support. Patients described experiences of disrespect, lack</p>

							<p>of confidentiality, and unwelcoming treatment.</p> <p>Across all facilities, patients emphasized that not being shouted at was a critical factor motivating continued engagement in care, regardless of facility proximity to their work or home.</p>
Sikombe et al. 2025[32]	Zambia	To evaluate whether a multicomponent person-centred care (PCC) intervention targeting healthcare worker behaviour could improve 1) client experience, 2) missed visits, 3) retention, and 4) treatment success (VS) among people living with HIV	Quantitative RCT Stepped-wedge, cluster-randomized design (Intervention): clinic staff trained in person-centred care, communication skills, and stress management, plus regular mentorship; client feedback for HCW reflection and service improvement; and biannual performance incentives (up to	Client exit surveys, electronic health record (EHR) data, viral load records, and mentorship logs	Adults living with HIV aged 18 years or older - Receiving HIV care in Zambia - Includes both men and women	177,543 unique clients	The PCC intervention significantly reduced poor visit experiences from 23.3% (control) to 13.3%, reduced missed visits from 25.3% (control) to 22.6%, and improved 15-month retention from 80.2% (control) to 83.6% (intervention). There was no significant effect on VS at 15 months: control (83.7%) versus intervention (83.8%).

			US\$75 per clinic) based on client rankings to motivate and reinforce positive behaviours.				
Arendse et al. 2024[24]	South Africa	<p>Primary aim: To evaluate the implementation of a Welcome Service intervention that aimed to support people re-engaging with primary care services after ART interruption, and to improve treatment outcomes.</p> <p>Secondary aim: To conduct a pre and post analysis of clinical outcomes using aggregated clinic-level routine health data, among all people accessing</p>	Mixed-methods evaluation of a Welcome service intervention: clinic staff trained and mentored to offer re-engaging patients, 4 months of enhanced care: triage by nurse or clerk; specialized counselling (return or treatment interruption) in addition to routine clinical management.	Qualitative in-depth interviews and collected quantitative program-monitoring data.	<p>Primary aim: Patients re-engaging in care (ART interruption for ≥ 56 days), - 68% were female and - Median age was 38 years (interquartile range, IQR, 32-44).</p> <p>HCWs (nurses, counsellors, and data clerks)</p> <p>Secondary aim: - All patients</p>	<p>Primary aim: 521 patients and 12 were HCWs (4 nurses, 6 counsellors, and 2 data clerks).</p> <p>Secondary aim: 7623 patients</p>	<p>Primary aim: The intervention resulted in positive care experiences. HCWs demonstrated improved awareness of how negative attitudes can harm patient engagement, although some continued to express judgment by expecting “justifiable” reasons for disengagement.</p> <p>Among the 521 re-engaging patients, 66% were retained at 4 months after re-engagement, and of those with a VL, 40% were undetectable (≤ 50 copies/mL). Using the 2023 WHO definition of VL suppression of < 1000 copies/mL, 88% were suppressed. There was no comparison group.</p> <p>Secondary aim: Difference-in-differences (DID) analysis comparing overall retention and VS in (whole) clinics that had the Welcome Service intervention to ones that</p>

		HIV healthcare services at the intervention sites, irrespective of whether they had an interruption in care or received the intervention.			(irrespective of having an ART interruption or receiving the intervention), - 18 years or older, - 73% were female - Median age was 42 years (IQR: 36–48). - Had an HIV-related healthcare visit during study enrolment period at intervention or non-intervention clinics		did not. There was a decline in retention in both intervention and comparison clinics compared to baseline, but the decline was slower at intervention clinics ($p < 0.001$). There was no statistically significant difference in VS.
Kolié et al. 2024[30]	Guinea	To describe the patient-provider relationship and explore challenges to optimal and	Qualitative	In-depth interviews and Focus Group Discussions	PLHIV: - Mean age: 41.7 years - 55% Women	15 patients Number of health providers not specified (2 individual in-	Interpersonal dynamics and psychosocial support were central to improving patient engagement and follow-up. Confidentiality, caring provider attitudes, and supportive patient-provider

		patient-centred care for PLHIV in Conakry, Guinea			Health providers (facility and services managers, and psychosocial counsellors). Participants were involved in 17 in-depth interviews and 5 focus group discussions.	depth interviews and about 6-10 providers in 5 Focus Group Discussions)	relationships facilitated engagement, and increased follow-up was linked to psychosocial support and respectful communication. However, several challenges hindered patient-centred care, including poor communication (e.g., delays in sharing lab or viral load results), financial burdens on patients, inadequate infrastructure, and shortages of healthcare staff. Providers also noted that respecting patients' choice of HIV care facility was important for supporting adherence and retention. Integrating psychosocial counsellors and addressing systemic challenges were identified as essential to achieving optimal patient-centred care.
Killian et al. 2024[25]	South Africa	To understand how negative clinic experiences affect engagement in HIV care and shape preferences for adherence support among PLHIV.	Qualitative	In-depth interviews and Focus Group Discussions	PLHIV aged 18 years or older. 2 groups: those who had either been on ART continuously for ≥ 6 months and had a viral load test result of >1000	41 Patients 20 providers (6 clinicians, 7 CHWs, 7 counsellors)	Negative interpersonal interactions were a major driver of disengagement. More than half of PLHIV reported negative clinic experiences (most commonly mistreatment by staff, fears of HIV status disclosure, and other structural inefficiencies). These reports were corroborated by 60% of healthcare providers, and negative experiences were more frequently reported by men.

				<p>copies/mL within the prior month or had returned after discontinuing care.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mean age of PLHIV: 37.4 years - 51% female <p>Providers (counsellors, clinicians [doctors and nurses], community health workers [CHWs])</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 18 years or older - Mean age of providers: 42 years - 90% female 	<p>Two-thirds of PLHIV with negative experiences described being shouted at, sworn at, talked down to, or embarrassed by staff when they missed doses or interrupted treatment. Such encounters generated fear, shame, and discomfort, leading to non-adherence to treatment and avoidance of clinics. Providers also acknowledged that patients often feel scared to return to care because of mistreatment.</p> <p>PLHIV who had negative experiences preferred non-clinic-based interventions, such as peer support groups and check-in text messages, rather than interventions delivered within clinic settings.</p>
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<p>Wachira et al. 2022[28]</p>	<p>Kenya</p>	<p>Primary aim: To assess the impact of a patient-centered intervention referred to as enhanced patient care (EPC) on VS among unsuppressed patients living with HIV in Kenya.</p> <p>Secondary aim: To assess the impact of the intervention on clinic appointment adherence and clinicians' provider-patient communication (PPC) skills.</p>	<p>Quantitative Pilot RCT at two clinics, one clinic randomized to intervention and other to control (three study arms). HCWs in the intervention clinic trained on principles of motivational interviewing, patients' expectations and inter-cultural sensitivity during clinical encounters, and implementation of EPC. The EPC package included an assigned clinician for continuity; treatment dialogues on viral load/barriers with written summaries reviewed with</p>	<p>Patient medical records review (prospective) and surveys at baseline and 6 months post-intervention.</p>	<p>Adult PLHIV aged 48 years (SD: 12.05 years) - majority female (56%) - on a first-line ART regimen with elevated viral loads</p>	<p>328 patients: Intervention clinic (Two study arms; 110 patients in PPC training + EPC; 110 in PPC training + SOC) Control clinic (One study arm; 108 patients in SOC only)</p>	<p>Six months post-intervention, VS was highest among participants in PPC training + EPC (84.4%) and PPC training + Standard of care [SOC] (83.7%), compared with 64.4% in SOC alone ($P \leq 0.001$). Participants in the SOC arm had significantly lower odds of VS compared to those in the PPC + EPC arm (odds ratio = 0.36, 95% CI: 0.18 to 0.72).</p> <p>No significant difference in VS was found between PPC training + EPC and PPC training + SOC, suggesting that PPC training itself may have been the primary driver of improved VS outcomes by strengthening clinicians' communication and patient-engagement skills.</p>
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			assistance of peer supporters after consultation and flexible patient-chosen scheduling.				
Lowane et al. 2022[26]	South Africa	To explore and describe professional nurses' perspectives on factors contributing to missed appointments by patients on ART in selected community health centres	Qualitative Descriptive and contextual	In-depth individual interviews	Professional nurses (NIMART-trained) - Participants aged 20–49 years, 9 (64%) were females	14 nurses	The findings suggest that patient-centred, respectful communication and participatory scheduling are critical for supporting retention in HIV care and reducing missed appointments. Missed appointments are influenced by interpersonal factors such as scolding, poor communication, and lack of respect from HCWs), alongside a range of administrative and systemic factors that further hinder patient engagement in care.
Hurley et al. 2018[29]	Mali	To understand the features of positive PPC and their potential for promoting engagement and re-engagement in ART programs in Bamako, Mali.	Qualitative	In-depth interviews and focus group discussions	PLHIV engaged and reengaging in care Healthcare providers (Physician, Psychosocial Counsellor, Administrator, Pharmacist)	69 patients and 17 providers	Effective PPC supports sustained engagement in HIV care by building rapport, addressing emotional needs, eliciting patient perspectives, and partnering with them to resolve conflicts. Positive PPC, characterised by emotional understanding, encouraging patient expression, and meaningful collaboration, enhances patients' sense of being known and valued, which strengthens

							connectedness to care and improves appointment-keeping and re-engagement.
Shabalala et al. 2018[31]	eSwatini	To explores HIV positive clients' reasons for discontinuing ART under the MaxART test and treat implementation study in eSwatini.	Qualitative	Semi-structured face-to-face interviews	Adult PLHIV and ART-naive clients.	10 participants (9 clients and one treatment supporter).	<p>Although mobility was a primary trigger for missed visits, respondents emphasized that negative interpersonal experiences with healthcare providers also influenced disengagement from care. Perceived lack of empathy, attention, and respectful communication, such as being shouted at, spoken to harshly, or made to feel uncared for, left respondents feeling hurt, angry, and humiliated, contributing to decisions to stop ART.</p> <p>Ultimately, disengagement resulted from respondents navigating complex social, economic, and medical pressures or circumstances, with emotional responses to negative provider interactions and stigma compounding the practical challenges driving loss to follow-up.</p>

Wachira et al. 2018[27]	Kenya	To explore HIV patients' perceptions, experiences and expectations of their engagement in care.	Qualitative	In-depth interviews and focus group discussions	PLHIV 18 years and older, - Median age was 37 years, - 48 (56%) were females	86 patients	The study findings suggest that patient engagement in HIV care is strongly shaped by interpersonal quality of care. Patients expressed a desire for active involvement in decision-making, including clear explanations, consideration of their opinions, consent-seeking, and collaborative treatment planning. They valued providers who were welcoming, empathetic, and concerned with patients' social wellbeing. Providers who demonstrated respect through rapport-building, positive talk, and social chitchat were perceived as more patient-centred and better able to facilitate engagement. Patients also identified personal and contextual factors influencing engagement, highlighting the importance of supportive interpersonal behaviours within rational professional boundaries.
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References

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